

Theoretical Calculation of the Optical and EPR Spectra for VO²⁺ in Zinc Lactate Trihydrate Single Crystal

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Received: 8 April 2016; Published online: 1 October 2016

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Abstract

The optical and electron paramagnetic resonance (EPR) spectra for VO²⁺ ion in zinc lactate trihydrate (ZLT) single crystals are calculated using perturbation theory method (PTM). The calculated optical absorption bands and spin-Hamiltonian parameters are in reasonable agreement with the experimental values. It appears that theoretical method used is effective in explaining optical and EPR spectra of 3d¹ ion in crystals.

Keywords: A. Single crystal; D. Crystal fields; D. Optical properties; D. Electron paramagnetic resonance

1. Introduction

Electron paramagnetic resonance (EPR) is one of the most important tools for the experimental study of chemical bonding of paramagnetic centers (Kripal et al, 2010; Poonguzhali et al., 2000; Song et al., 013). The optical absorption provides the energy level structure of the metal ion (Feng, 2007; 2009). Thus, EPR and optical absorption techniques are two powerful tools for studying dynamic behaviour of the transition ions in crystals. The vanadyl, VO²⁺ ion having 3d¹ configuration is the most stable cation used extensively as a probe for finding the site symmetry of central ion and its bonding with various ligands employing EPR studies (Kripal et al, 2010; Poonguzhali et al., 2000; Kripal and Shukla, 2011; Sivprasad et al., 1990; Kripal and Singh, 2006). Moreover, due to strong V=O bonding in VO²⁺ ion, most of the VO²⁺ complexes possess C_{4v} symmetry with both *g* and *A* values being axially symmetric (Kripal and Shukla, 2011; Sivprasad et al., 1990). Kripal et al. (2006) measured the optical spectra and EPR parameters for VO²⁺ in ZLT single crystal. As is known, for 3d¹ (VO²⁺ or V⁴⁺) ion in crystals, an octahedral complex with a tetragonal compression would give $g_{\parallel} < g_{\perp} < g_s$ and $|A_{\parallel}| > |A_{\perp}|$ (Wei, 2010; Karabulut and Tufan, 2008), where *g_s* is the free-spin *g* value (= 2.0023). The observed EPR parameters of ZLT: VO²⁺ agree with the above relation.

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In this investigation, the optical and EPR spectra of VO^{2+} doped ZLT single crystal are calculated using perturbation theory method (PTM) for a $3d^1$ ion in tetragonally compressed octahedron. In the calculation, the tetragonal field parameters D_s and D_t are estimated from the superposition model which makes it possible to correlate the crystal-field parameters and hence the EPR parameters with the tetragonal distortion $\Delta R (= R_{\perp} - R_{\parallel})$ of $(\text{VO}_6)^{8-}$ cluster in ZLT single crystal. On the basis of above, useful information of defect structure for the tetragonal VO^{2+} ions in ZLT single crystal can be obtained.

2. Crystal Structure

The crystal structure of zinc lactate trihydrate, $\text{Zn}(\text{CH}_3\text{CHOHCOOH})_2 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ is monoclinic having space group $\text{P}2_1/\text{c}$, and the unit cell dimensions are $a = 9.38 \text{ \AA}$, $b = 5.83 \text{ \AA}$ and $c = 22.00 \text{ \AA}$, $Z = 4$ and angle $\beta = 90.9^\circ$ (Song et al., 2013; Singh et al., 1975). The six oxygen atoms, two from water molecules and four from two lactate groups are nearest neighbors of Zn and they form a distorted octahedron around the zinc atom as shown in Fig.1. All three water molecules inter in hydrogen bonding, and hydroxyl groups in molecules are also involved. A network of hydrogen bonds plays an important role in stabilization of the structure.

Fig. 1. Surroundings of VO^{2+} ion in ZLT

3. Theoretical Calculation

For a $3d^1$ ion in tetragonally compressed octahedron, its higher orbital doublet 2E_g splits into two orbital singlets ${}^2B_{1g}$ ($|dx^2-y^2\rangle$) and ${}^2A_{1g}$ ($|dz^2\rangle$), while the lower orbital triplet ${}^2T_{2g}$ splits into an orbital doublet ${}^2E_{1g}$ ($|dxz\rangle$ and $|dyz\rangle$) and a singlet ${}^2B_{2g}$ ($|dxy\rangle$), latter being the lowest (Wu et al., 2008; Fang et al., 2008). Thus, the three optical absorption bands can be given as:

$$\begin{aligned}
 E_1 &= E(^2B_{2g}) \rightarrow E(^2B_{1g}) = 10Dq \\
 E_2 &= E(^2B_{2g}) \rightarrow E(^2E_{1g}) = -3Ds + 5Dt \\
 E_3 &= E(^2B_{2g}) \rightarrow E(^2A_{1g}) = 10Dq - 4Ds - 5Dt.
 \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

The cubic and tetragonal field parameters (Dq , Ds and Dt) can be determined from the superposition model (Fang et al., 2008; Li et al., 2015) and the following relations:

$$\begin{aligned}
 Dq &= \frac{3}{4} \bar{A}_4(R) \\
 Ds &= \frac{4}{7} \bar{A}_2(R) \left[\left(\frac{\bar{R}}{R_{\parallel}} \right)^{t_2} - \left(\frac{\bar{R}}{R_{\perp}} \right)^{t_2} \right] \\
 Dt &= \frac{16}{21} \bar{A}_4(R) \left[\left(\frac{\bar{R}}{R_{\parallel}} \right)^{t_4} - \left(\frac{\bar{R}}{R_{\perp}} \right)^{t_4} \right]
 \end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

Here, $t_2 \approx 3$ and $t_4 \approx 5$ are the power-law exponents (Newman and Ng, 1989; Dong et al., 2004; Lin et al., 2006). $\bar{R} = (R_{\parallel} + 2R_{\perp})/3$ is the average impurity-ligand (V-O) distance, where R_{\parallel} is the (V-O) distance along the C_4 axis, and R_{\perp} is the bond length between V^{4+} and the planar oxygen ions.

$\bar{A}_2(R)$ and $\bar{A}_4(R)$ are the intrinsic parameters, where the reference distance R ($\approx R_{\perp} \approx 2.141 \text{ \AA}$ (Gong et al., 2010)) is taken for the VO^{2+} in cubic field. For $3d^n$ ions in octahedral coordination, the ratio $\bar{A}_2(R) / \bar{A}_4(R)$ is in the range of 9–12 (Feng, 2007, 2009; Wu et al., 2008; Fang et al., 2008;

Kuang et al., 2012; Zhang et al., 2014; Huang et al., 2013). Here, we take $\bar{A}_2(R) / \bar{A}_4(R) \approx 9.5$. The third-order perturbation formulae of EPR parameters (g factors g_{\parallel} , g_{\perp} and the hyperfine structure constants A_{\parallel} , A_{\perp}) for $3d^1$ ions in tetragonal symmetry with the ground state $^2B_{2g}$ ($|dxy\rangle$) are obtained as (Wei, 2010; Huang et al., 2013):

$$\begin{aligned}
 g_{\parallel} &= g_s - 8k \frac{\xi}{E_2} - (k + g_s) \frac{\xi^2}{E_2^2} + 4k \frac{\xi^2}{E_1 E_2} \\
 g_{\perp} &= g_s - 2k \frac{\xi}{E_1} + (k - g_s) \frac{\xi^2}{E_1^2} - 2g_s \frac{\xi^2}{E_2^2}
 \end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

$$A_{\parallel} = P \left[\left(-K - \frac{4}{7} \right) + (g_{\parallel} - g_{\perp}) + \frac{3}{7} (g_{\perp} - g_{\parallel}) \right]$$

$$A_{\perp} = P \left[\left(-K + \frac{2}{7} \right) + \frac{11}{14} (g_{\perp} - g_{\parallel}) \right]$$

In the above formulae, k is the orbital reduction factor. ξ and P are, respectively, the spin-orbit coupling coefficient and the dipolar hyperfine structure parameter for $3d^1$ ion in crystals. K is the isotropic core polarization constant. In general, the value of K is in the range 0.6–1.0 for VO^{2+} ion in various crystals (Feng, 2007, 2009; Karabulut and Tufan, 2008; Kuang et al., 2012; Zhang et al., 2014; Huang et al., 2013; Li and Zheng, 2014; Zheng et al., 2008). Here, we take $K \approx 0.86$, which is comparable with the value of K (≈ 0.72) obtained earlier (Fang et al., 2008). Thus, the anisotropy Δg ($= g_{\parallel} - g_{\perp}$) is connected with the tetragonal field parameters and hence with the local structure of the studied system. Considering covalency effect for $3d^n$ ions in crystals, we have (Zhang et al., 2014; Huang et al., 2013; Li and Zheng, 2014; Zheng et al., 2008)

$$\xi = N^2 \xi_0 \quad \text{and} \quad P = N^2 P_0. \quad (4)$$

where N ($\approx K$) is the covalency reduction factor. Thus, the spin-orbit coupling coefficient ξ and the dipolar hyperfine structure parameter P can be obtained for the studied system by using the free-ion data ξ_0 ($\approx 248 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (Griffith, 1964)) and P_0 ($\approx 172 \times 10^{-4} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (Mc Garvey, 1967)) for VO^{2+} ion. By fitting the calculated optical and EPR spectra to the experimental values, one gets

$$N \approx 0.861, \quad \bar{A}_4(R) \approx 2550 \text{ cm}^{-1} \quad \text{and} \quad R_{\parallel} \approx 1.965 \text{ \AA}. \quad (5)$$

The calculated results are compared with the experimental values in Table 1 and Table 2. The obtained V-O distance along C_4 axis ($R_{\parallel} \approx 1.965 \text{ \AA}$) is close to $R_{\parallel} \approx 1.984 \text{ \AA}$ (Feng, 2007; 2009).

4. Result and Discussion

Table 1 The calculated and experimental EPR parameters (g factors and the hyperfine structure constants (in 10^{-4} cm^{-1})) for ZLT: VO^{2+} single crystal.

	g factors		Hyperfine structure constants (in 10^{-4} cm^{-1})	
	g_{\parallel}	g_{\perp}	A_{\parallel}	A_{\perp}
Cal.	1.9133	1.9841	203	83
Expt. (Kripal and Singh, 2006)	1.9236	1.9999	197	90

Table 2 The calculated and experimental optical parameters for ZLT: VO²⁺ single crystal.

	Octahedral and Tetragonal parameters(cm ⁻¹)			Optical absorption bands (in cm ⁻¹)		
	Dq	Ds	Dt	² B _{2g} → ² E _{1g}	² B _{2g} → ² B _{1g}	² B _{2g} → ² A _{1g}
Cal.	1912	-2987	1194	15,031	19,120	25,103
Expt. (Kripal and Singh, 2006)	1988	-2800	1265	14,727	19,880	24,752

From Table 1&Table 2, one can find that the calculated EPR and optical spectra are in reasonable agreement with the observed values. Thus, the optical and EPR spectra of VO²⁺ doped ZLT are quantitatively interpreted and the local defect structure of the octahedral (VO₆)⁸⁻ cluster in the crystal is established. The value $R_{\perp} > R_{\parallel}$ indicates that the studied (VO₆)⁸⁻ cluster exists in a tetragonally distorted octahedral site compressed along the C₄-axis, which is consistent with the experimental EPR results ($g_{\parallel} < g_{\perp} < g_s$ and $|A_{\parallel}| > |A_{\perp}|$).

The validity of the covalency factor N can be further illustrated using $N^2 \approx 1 - h(L)k(M)$ (Zhang and Wan, 2013), where the parameter $h(L)$ (≈ 1) is the characteristic of the ligands L ($= O^{2-}$), and $k(M)$ is the characteristic of the central metal ion (Li et al., 2015). From the values $k(V^{2+}) \approx 0.1$ (Li et al., 2015) and $k(V^{3+}) \approx 0.2$ (Li et al., 2015), one can reasonably obtain $k(V^{4+}) \approx 0.3$. Thus, we have N of about 0.84, which is close to $N \approx 0.861$ taken here and can be considered as reasonable.

The above calculations suggested that the hyperfine structure constants A_{\parallel} and A_{\perp} of VO²⁺ in ZLT single crystal are negative (see Table 1), but the observed values given in reference (Kripal and Singh, 2006) are positive. It should be noted that the signs of constants A_{\parallel} and A_{\perp} cannot be determined only from EPR measurement (Havlicek et al., 1974). Thus, the experimental values of constants A_{\parallel} and A_{\perp} are actually absolute values (Kripal and Shukla, 2011; Sivprasad et al., 1990; Kripal and Singh, 2006). In the present paper, we found that the signs of A_{\parallel} and A_{\perp} for VO²⁺ in ZLT single crystal should be negative. This is consistent with other theoretical investigations (Feng, 2007, 2009; Wei, 2010; Zhang et al., 2014; Huang et al., 2013; Li and Zheng, 2014; Zheng et al., 2008). Therefore, the calculated values of A_{\parallel} and A_{\perp} for ZLT: VO²⁺ are reasonable in signs as well as in magnitude.

5. Conclusions

The optical and EPR spectra of VO²⁺ in ZLT single crystal are theoretically investigated using PTM. The calculated results are in good agreement with the observed ones. Large tetragonally compressed distortion ΔR ($= 0.176 \text{ \AA}$) of (VO₆)⁸⁻ cluster in ZLT single crystal is reasonably established.

References

Dong, H. N. Li, P. (2010). Theoretical studies of the g factors and local structure for the tetragonal Nd3+

- center in SrTiO₃. Spectrochim. Acta A 76, 33-36.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.saa.2010.02.041>
- Dong, H. N. Wu, S. Y. Li, P. (2004). Theoretical explanation of EPR parameters for Cu²⁺ ion in TiO₂ crystal. Phys. Status Solidi B 241, 1935-1938.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.1002/pssb.200402033>
- Fang, W. Zheng, W. C. He, L. (2008). Investigation of the Optical and EPR spectra for VO₂⁺ in LiKSO₄ crystal. Spectrochim. Acta A 71, 513-515.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.saa.2007.12.035>
- Feng, W. L. (2009). Theoretical studies of optical and EPR spectra for vanadyl ion in alkaline earth aluminoborate glasses. Phil. Mag. 89, 1391-1394; (2007). Investigations of the optical and EPR spectra for VO₂⁺ in NaHC₂O₄.H₂O single Crystals. Phil. Mag. Lett. 87(2007) 663-667.
- Garvey, B. R. Mc (1967). The isotropic hyperfine interaction. J. Phys. Chem. 71, 51-66.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.1021/j100860a007>
- Gong, J. T. Wang, L. J. Feng, W. L. (2010). Theoretical studies of optical spectra and EPR parameters for V⁴⁺ impurity ions in CoMTH. Spectrosc. Lett. 43, 306-309.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/00387010903348284>
- Griffith, J. S. The Theory of Transition-Metal Ions, Cambridge University Press, London, 1964.
- Havlicek, V. Novak, P. Mill, B. V. (1974). EPR of V⁴⁺ ion in several garnet system. Phys. Status Solidi B 64, K19-K23.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.1002/pssb.2220640152>
- Huang, Y. P. Zhang, Z. Yu, B. L. (2013). Theoretical explanation of electron paramagnetic resonance spectral data in vanadyl doped CdNaPO₄.6H₂O crystal. Optik 124, 4533-4535.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ijleo.2013.01.040>
- Karabulut, B. Tufan, A. (2008). An EPR and optical absorption study VO₂⁺ ions in diammonium hydrogen citrate single crystals. Spectrochim. Acta A 69, 642-646.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.saa.2007.05.015>
- Kripal, R. Mishra, I. Gupta, S. K. Arora, M. (2010). EPR and optical absorption studies on VO₂⁺ ions in calcium fumarate trihydrate single crystals. Chem. Phys. Lett. 484, 200-206.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.cplett.2009.11.038>
- Kripal, R. Shukla, S. (2011). EPR and optical absorption study of VO₂⁺ doped Lithium hydroxylammonium sulphate. Spectrosc. Lett. 44, 235-243.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/00387010.2010.506905>
- Kripal, R. Singh, P. (2006). EPR and optical absorption studies on VO₂⁺ ions in zinc lactate trihydrate. J. Magn. Mater. 307, 308-312.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jmmm.2006.04.033>
- Kuang, M. Q. Wu, S. Y. Zhang, H. M. (2012). Theoretical studies on local structure spin Hamiltonian parameters for the orthorhombic Cu²⁺ center in LiNbO₃. Optik 123, 1601-1604.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ijleo.2011.08.032>
- Li, C. Y. Wang, G. X. Zheng, X. M. (2015). Theoretical studies of the optical and EPR spectra for VO₂⁺ in Na₃C₆H₅O₇.2H₂O single crystal. Condens. Matter Phys. 18, 23701: 1-5.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.physb.2015.09.018>
- Li, C. Y. Zheng, X. M. (2014). Theoretical studies of the local structure and EPR spectra for VO₂⁺ in MB4O7 glasses. Acta Phys. Polon. A 125, 73-76.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.12693/APhysPolA.125.73>
- Lin, J. Z. Wu, S.Y. Fu, Q. Lu, G. D. (2006). Investigation of the Spin Hamiltonian Parameters of a Tetragonal VO₂⁺ Center in (NH₄)₂SbCl₅. Z. Naturforsch. A 61, 583- 587.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.1515/zna-2006-10-1111>

- Newman, D. J. Ng, B. (1989) .The Superposition model of crystal fields. Rep. Prog. Phys. 52, 699-763.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.1088/0034-4885/52/6/002>
- Poonguzhali, R. Venkatesan, R. Rajendiran, T. M. Rao, P. S. Ravikumar, R. V. S. S. N. Reddy, Y. P. (2000). Spectral studies on VO₂⁺ doped MPPH crystals. Cryst. Res. Technol. 35, 1203-1207.
[http://dx.doi.org/10.1002/1521-4079\(200010\)35:10<1203::AID-CRAT1203>3.0.CO;2-I](http://dx.doi.org/10.1002/1521-4079(200010)35:10<1203::AID-CRAT1203>3.0.CO;2-I)
- Singh, K. D. Jain, S. C. Sakore, T. D. Biswas, A. B. (1975).The crystal and molecular structure of zinc lactate trihydrate. Acta Cryst. B31, 990-993.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.1107/S0567740875004359>
- Sivaprasad, P. Ramesh, K. Reddy, Y. P. (1990). EPR and optical studies of VO₂⁺ and Cu²⁺ Rb₂Cd(SO₄)₂.6H₂O. J. Phys.: Condens. Matter 2, 5595-5602.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.1088/0953-8984/2/25/011>
- Song, B. T. Wu, S. Y. Kuang, M. Q. Hu, X. F. (2013). Studies on local structure and the EPR parameters for the tetragonal Pt³⁺ center in PbTiO₃. Optik 124, 2493-2495.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ijleo.2012.08.012>
- Wei, Q. (2010). Investigation of the Optical and EPR Spectra for Cr³⁺ ions in Diammonium Hexaaqua Magnesium Sulphate single crystal. Acta Phys. Pol. A 117, 962-964.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.12693/APhysPolA.117.962>
- Wu, S. Y. Wei, L. H. Zhang, Z. H. Wang, X. F. Lin, J. Z. (2008). Investigations of the Spin Hamiltonian Parameters and the Local Structures of the Substitutional V⁴⁺ Centres in Rutile-Type MO₂ (M = Sn, Ti, Ge) Z. Naturforsch. A 63, 523- 528.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.1515/zna-2008-7-821>
- Zhang, H. M. Wan, X. (2013). Theoretical studies of spin Hamiltonian parameters for the tetragonally elongated Cu²⁺ centers in ARB₄O₇ glasses. J. Non-Cryst. Solids 361, 43-46.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jnoncrsol.2012.10.019>
- Zhang, H. M. Xiao, W. B. Wan, X. (2014). Theoretical studies of the optical and EPR spectra for VO₂⁺ in MgKPO₄.6H₂O single crystal. Physica B 449, 225-228.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.physb.2014.05.036>
- Zheng, W. C. He, L. Fang, W. Liu, H. G. (2008). Theoretical studies of the optical spectrum band positions and spin Hamiltonian parameters for VO₂⁺ ions in MgNH₄PO₆.6H₂O crystals for three microscopic methods. Physica B 403, 4171-4173.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.physb.2008.09.001>